

ISic3083

I.Sicily inscription 3083

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Chiesa di San Francesco

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI331392

1. Πρειγομ-

2. ενία ²⁶Πριμογενία²⁶ □ έτ-

3. [ώ]ν □ πε'. □

4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284926

EDCS 64900559

PHI 331392

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 36.0832

Brugnone, A. 1984-1985. Epigrafia greca. *Kokalos*. 30-31: 231-255. At 249-250
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